

Clean Technology Through Bio Char to Enhance Soil and Water Quality

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Abstract

The ancient indigenous knowledge preserved in Amazonian Dark Earths (ADEs), a type of extremely fertile soil that contains large amounts of charcoal and archaeological artifacts and is typically high in calcium and phosphorus, is the source of inspiration for the potential use of bio char in modern agriculture. The humid tropics face significant challenges when it comes to sustainable soil fertility management. As a result, ADEs have raised public awareness by serving as an example of how soil fertility improvements and long-term carbon sequestration can coexist. This has increased interest in bio char, a traditional method converted into carbon. The surge in food demand and environmental concerns provide numerous obstacles for modern agriculture. The potential applications of bio char in carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emission reduction, renewable energy, waste mitigation, and soil amendment are becoming more and more acknowledged by scientists and policy makers. The use of bio char in soil has the potential to significantly impact the dynamics of nutrients, soil pollutants, and microbial functions. Consequently, applying bio char to soil strategically may have positive effects on agriculture, the environment, and the economy. Additionally, recent research has demonstrated that bio char plays an important role as a soil conditioner and fertilizer to increase crop output as well as improve soil quality and health. Applying bio char as a soil supplement appears to improve soil nutrient density, water-holding capacity, fertilizer requirements, improve soil microbiology, and boost crop yields. Furthermore, using bio char has a number of positive effects on the environment, the economy, and possible integration with carbon credit schemes. The solution to these basic needs could be found in bio char, also referred to as bio carbon.

Keywords: *bio char, soil amendment, sustainability, carbon sequestration, soil conditioner*

INTRODUCTION

The global economy is shaped in large part by agriculture. Nowadays, one of the main concerns is food security. Even with the tremendous improvements in farming techniques following World War II, the world's food supply still cannot meet current demand. In addition, there are still concerns related to soil contamination, climate change, and desertification that need to be resolved for the agriculture industry [Pullagurala et al;2018]. With a growing population, it

is predicted that global food demand will rise by 70% by 2050 [Samantarai et al;2014], and achieving this demand without sacrificing the health of the soil and the agro ecosystem has become a major concern for the agriculture industry. Bio char as a soil amendment has been suggested as a tactic for mitigating climate change as well as enhancing soil quality and production because of the benefits of improved soil characteristics and long-term carbon collection. Since burning crop leftovers releases black carbon in the form of dispersed particulate matter, which can contaminate surrounding metropolitan areas, burning crop residues is becoming a major problem in most nations. Consequently, one of the practical methods for increasing the rates at which carbon is naturally sequestered in the soil, lowering agricultural waste, and enhancing soil quality is the pyrolysis process of turning organic waste into bio char. The widespread use of pesticides, plant growth regulators, fertilizers, and other chemicals without thought has become the norm in response to the urgent need for food. Because of its detrimental effects on the ecology and the entire food chain, their overuse is a serious reason for concern. Significant risks to the sustainability of agricultural production in tropical regions include depletion of soil nutrients and organic matter, decline in agricultural productivity from overuse of chemical fertilizers, and changes in climate brought on by human activity. Thus, in order to preserve soil health and improve sustainability, it is becoming increasingly vital to utilize organic fertilizer in addition to inorganic fertilizer. In addition to organic manures and composts, using bio char is a relatively new strategy that could be advantageous for agriculture and the environment. In light of current and impending issues, bio char could hold the key to creating a sustainable future and incorporating valuable products into the circular economy model. Researchers hope to find a way to increase soil quality and boost agricultural sustainability by amending the soil with bio char [Samantarai et al; 2014]. A soil's texture, ability to support and maintain microbial activity, and capability to hold on to moisture and nutrients are factors that define its quality [Sandhu et al; 2017]. Although bio char is typically used untreated, new research indicates that it may be utilized to enhance performance through chemical or physical modification [Sun et al;2017]. Plant yields and soil health have been proven to benefit from bio char while maintaining the integrity of the soil [Bashir et al;2018].

BIO CHAR PRODUCTION PROCESS

When producing bio char, thermochemical conversion technologies are more widely used than biochemical ones because the latter produce hydrogen at a much slower rate and with a lower yield. Gasification, pyrolysis, and combustion are additional subcategories of the former. Figure: 1; depicts the several thermochemical reactions that go into the creation of bio char. With the primary objective of improving soil, bio char is a highly porous, fine-grained product rich in

paramagnetic centres of both organic and inorganic nature. It is obtained through slow pyrolysis of biomass waste, which can come from agricultural, municipal, animal, or industrial sources. A significant portion of its surface is covered in aromatic surfaces and oxygen functional groups. Between 300 to 1000°C are the typical pyrolysis temperatures used. Bio char, solid rich in carbon, is produced from the residue of pyrolysis, a fast-heating process that removes hydrogen and carbon monoxide from biomass in the absence of oxygen. An energy-dense liquid known as "bio-oil" can be created by capturing and condensing the volatile gases that are emitted during this process. more refinement can yield diesel and more hydrocarbon-based products. The carbonization of organic wastes produces bio char, which has been demonstrated to be a viable replacement that alters the physicochemical and biological properties [Zhang et al;2017] of soil in addition to influencing soil carbon.

Figure 1: Bio char Production Process

THE BENEFITS OF BIO CHAR ON SOIL HEALTH

A soil's ability to fulfill various agronomic and environmental tasks is referred to as its state of health. Response to management and inputs, resilience to biotic and abiotic stressors, and biomass/agronomic productivity are crucial among these roles. In agricultural land use, soil health pertains to the ability of the soil to preserve or enhance environmental quality while simultaneously supporting and fostering the growth of crops and animals. A soil management regime's success depends on maintaining a certain amount of soil organic matter and nutrient biological cycling. Erosion, compaction, salinization, nutrient shortage, loss of biodiversity, and

desertification are among the soil degradation processes that are facilitated by the reduction in SOM sequestration [Zhang et al., 2017].

IMPACT OF BIO CHAR ON THE ENVIRONMENT, SOIL HEALTH, AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY

Current conditions highlight the pressing challenges of food security, deteriorating soil fertility, climate change, and profitability. In view of the ongoing global climate change, soil carbon is crucial for food security, ecosystem health, and environmental durability. Pyrolysed agricultural residue, or bio char, has the ability to sequester carbon due to its biological origin and physico-chemical characteristics. Longer-term nutrient availability in accordance with crop needs is ensured by its increased resistance to decay and capacity to hold onto nutrients. Both direct and indirect effects on soil fertility are associated with the application of bio char. As for the indirect effects, they come from the improved physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the soil (Beusch, 2021, Singh et al., 2022). The direct effects include an enhanced nutrient availability (potassium [K], phosphorus [P], calcium [Ca], magnesium [Mg], and so on). According to studies conducted by Das et al. (2021), Singh et al. (2022) and Hu et al. (2023), the primary impacts on chemical and biological parameters are increases in soil pH, cation exchange capacity, mineral nitrogen (N) availability, dissolved organic carbon, and microbial diversity (bacterial and fungal). While a large body of research shows that applying bio char at higher rates to highly eroded, coarse-textured tropical soils improve soil quality parameters, very little to no effect has been found in other soil types, such as Mediterranean calcareous soils (Nogues et al., 2023).

THE CONTRIBUTION OF BIOCHAR TO INCREASING FERTILIZER EFFICIENCY

According to El-Sharkawy et al. (2022) there is evidence that applying biochar improves maize and wheat productivity and reduces abiotic pressures in saline-sodic soils. Although wood-based bio char is less effective than bio char made from manure, greenhouse waste, and grasses for supplementing nutrients, the potential for carbon sequestration of wood-based bio char is higher (Ippolito et al., 2020). Both the increased nutrient retention and the decreased leaching of applied fertilizers out of the soil-plant ecosystem are caused by bio char-amended soils' improved water-holding capacity and increased cation and anion exchange capabilities.

HOW BIOCHAR AFFECTS THE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SOIL

The physicochemical characteristics of damaged or nutrient-depleted soils may be improved by adding bio char as a soil amendment. The combination of surface functioning and porosity in bio char determines its capacity to hold onto soil water . Because of the porous internal structure of bio char, soil porosity is increased, aiding in the expansion of soil's surface area and

improving water penetration. According to earlier research, adding bio char to infertile soils increases total pore volume, reduces bulk density, and boosts water-holding capacity. Applying bio char lowered the tensile strength of soil cores, according to Chen et al. 2007, suggesting that using bio char can lower the likelihood of soil compaction. Thus, the amount of bio char amendment added to the soil appears to be correlated with enhanced soil aggregation. It appears that a recent Italian study on bio char made from forest biological mass supports these conclusions (Baiamonte et al., 2021).

EFFECT OF BIOCHAR ON SOIL BIODIVERSITY

The diversity, abundance, and activity of soil biotic communities are likely to be impacted by the addition of bio char to soils as opposed to the addition of fresh organic matter [Lehman et al; 2011]. Bio char's very porous nature allows it to change biological functionality by affecting the availability of substrate and enzyme activity on or around bio char particles, as well as helping to provide a habitat for microorganisms [Gomez et al ;2014]. Microbial biomass and composition may be impacted by bio char, and bacteria have the power to modify the material's characteristics [Lehman et al; 2011]. According to Abujabhah et al. 2016, the addition of bio char increased microbial abundance. Soil microorganisms may be physically protected by the pores of bio char. Microbial activity, variety, and abundance are significantly influenced by soil response. In instances where it does not alter the pore volume or other physical and chemical features of the soil, bio char itself is resistant to microbial breakdown, therefore significant changes in microbial populations or biomasses should not be anticipated (Soenne et al., 2020). In the microhabitats within the bio char particles, the buffering ability of the soil solution provided by the CEC of bio char may also aid in reducing pH variations and maintaining ideal pH levels [Rousk et al;2010]. Research has indicated that the use of fertilizer combined with bio char enhanced microbial biomass in comparison to mineral fertilizer. In soils when leaching has occurred, microbial immobilization is a crucial strategy for retaining nitrogen. A higher N demand is caused by increased microbial activity stimulated by increased C availability, which encourages NO₃-immobilization and recycling. In phosphate-rich soils, bio char increased PSM activity for P mobilization; in P-deficient soils, bio char greatly increased crop production [Deb et al;2017].

IMPACT OF BIOCHAR ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Bio char has been noted to have a significant impact on carbon emissions and to be crucial for achieving global climate targets [Woolf et al;2016]. Although adding bio char to soils boosts agricultural yields significantly, bio char-bioenergy systems can be a valuable part of a worldwide plan since they aid with carbon capture and storage at lower carbon prices. Therefore, the efficient

use of bio char is crucial for sequestering carbon. The combustion of fossil fuels and the breakdown of biomass release an excessive amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere these days, raising the atmospheric carbon content daily. Because bio char may store 50% of the carbon in feedstock, its application aids in reducing carbon dioxide emissions [Sohi et al;2010]. Because of its exceptional stability, bio char can considerably reduce the amount of carbon dioxide released during organic decomposition. In order for it to be crucial in tracking the soil's release of nitrogen dioxide and methane, which are now the main contributors to climate change. Offsite pollution can also be decreased by applying bio char to the soil. It contributes to minimizing soil nutrient loss into groundwater and enhancing soil nutrient retention, particularly in phosphorus and nitrogen. Therefore, it has a significant impact on preventing nutrient erosion and increasing nutrient availability for crop production. A considerable reduction in the phosphorous mobility of animal manures can be obtained through pyrolysis [Venkatesh et al;2018]. This method also helps to lighten and reduce the volume of the manures, which will facilitate their disposal. Additionally, it facilitates the transformation of the manure's soluble inorganic phosphate into adsorbed phosphate. Several organic contaminants in the environment bond to bio char in an essential way. The adsorption of organic pollutants on bio char as well as their transport and destiny have been found to be significantly impacted by the heavy metals found in the soil. Since bio char is a naturally occurring substance, it has a strong affinity for organic contaminants, such as persistent organic pollutants (POPs), which can be adsorbed by it. Sites contaminated by heavy metals may benefit from the use of bio char in conjunction with phytoremediation techniques to stabilize and clean the area. However, several scientists have issued health advisories about the dangers of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon exposure (Zhang et al; 2021).

CONSTRAINTS IN BIO CHAR APPLICATIONS

As a value-added product of pyrolysis, bio char has been hailed for some time for its ability to enhance and preserve soil fertility and health while also increasing the advantages of storing carbon in the atmosphere. For several hours, the temperature of kilns used for its production must be kept between 400 and 700 C, producing carbon gases and a significant amount of thermal energy. The agronomic efficiency of bio char is difficult to predict because there haven't been many research done in various soil types, climatic zones, and land use scenarios. Prior to the establishment of commercial-scale pyrolysis facilities, the heterogeneous nature and manufacturing cost of bio char will continue to be a significant barrier for research and field use. [Par mar et al; 2014] are a few experimental restrictions on the application of bio char in agricultural systems.

1. Lack of enough bio char to be used on a large scale
2. Dry bio char's susceptibility to wind erosion;
3. Local farming communities' lack of adoption of bio char;
4. A shortage of sufficient farm labor; and
5. The high wages associated with gathering and processing crop residues
6. Insufficient agricultural equipment for crop residue recycling on-farm
7. Insufficient rewards for crop residue recycling.

The use of contaminated feed stocks or improper process conditions, such as temperatures above 500°C, during the synthesis of bio char might lead to contamination risk of bio char with heavy metals, dioxins, and Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. Reduced integration of bio char into soils due to the removal of crop remains from the field for bio char synthesis affects numerous soil parameters. Earthworm survival rates may be negatively impacted in some circumstances by the application of bio char at an exceptionally high rate [Venkatesh et al; 2017&2018].

DECREASING THE EMISSIONS OF GHG (GREEN HOUSE GAS)

Although the application of bio char has been shown in multiple studies to lower soil greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Zhang et al., 2020), the exact processes by which bio char reduces soil GHG emissions remain unknown. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emission is influenced by the charcoal feedstock, pyrolysis conditions, C:N ratio, and application rates. However, following the application of bio char, reports of an increase in soil methane (CH₄) and CO₂ emissions were also made (Mukherjee and Lal, 2013).

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In the agriculture sector primarily, adding bio char to soils can be one of the finest ways to combat biotic stress and boost crop output. As this chapter has covered, pyrolysis could be one of the processes that has greatly impacted the properties of bio char. As a result, bio char seems like a very promising solution for removing pollutants. When creating recoverable bio char for a variety of environmental applications, economic effects and recyclability should be taken into account. Despite the current surge in interest in bio char usage, there remains a significant information vacuum that requires attention. It is yet unknown what will happen to bio char in the end when it is used in the field and how it will affect soil quality in the long run. Further investigation is required into the effects of bio char on the microbial populations, soil physicochemical characteristics, and alterations in biogeochemical cycles [Ding *et al.*, 2016]. As soils are altered using bio char, researchers must look for ways to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions [Mandal *et al.*, 2016].

CONCLUSION

The loss of agricultural land due to population growth must be managed by implementing sustainable crop production methods. While direct crop residue integration preserves soil nutrients and organic carbon content, it also causes significant crop management issues by delaying the breakdown process. Over a decade, a great deal of research has been done on the effectiveness of bio char in enhancing crop productivity, environmental mitigation, reclamation of land, and soil health. Depending on the kind of soil, crop, type of bio char, and setting, this research has revealed a range of results, from noticeable improvements in soil health to essentially no change when compared to the control. Large-scale field trials have produced relatively little information thus far, presumably as a result of the high price of bio char on the market. Perhaps the most promising uses would be in very specialized applications to deal with certain environmental issues. When employing bio char as a strategy for sequestering carbon dioxide, it is important to take into account the global greenhouse gas emissions associated with its production and the need for an appropriate regulatory framework to mitigate any potential dangers of soil contamination caused by pollutants found in the material. Understanding how to modify the properties of bio char is crucial for the deployment of bio char in the future so that the amendment can be specifically tailored to each region, crop type, climate, and soil. Overall, research shows that bio char improves crop yields and soil quality, but there may be certain limitations that need to be investigated. The greatest quality of bio char should be seen as its diversity. Bio char appears to be a substance that could be customized to address specific problems in agriculture. Because of its physical-chemical characteristics, bio char can be utilized for water purification, reducing the bioavailability of pollutants that harm living things, and sequestering carbon from soil. In practical field situations, it is yet unclear how long-lasting the effects of bio char are on soil processes and mechanisms besides soil health, environmental quality, and long-term carbon sequestration can all be improved by adding bio char as a soil supplement.

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